

INTRAMYOMETRIAL INJECTION OF VASOPRESSIN TO MINIMIZE BLEEDING DURING CESAREAN HYSTERECTOMY OF PLACENTA ACRETA SPECTRUM

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ABSTRACT

To evaluate the efficacy and safety of intramyometrial vasopressin injection in reducing intraoperative blood loss and transfusion requirements during cesarean hysterectomy for placenta accreta spectrum (PAS).

Methodology:

A single-center, prospective, randomized controlled trial was conducted at MCH PIMS from January to March 2025. Sixty antenatal women diagnosed with major PAS by ultrasound were randomly allocated into two groups: Group A (n=30) received intramyometrial vasopressin (20 U in 19 mL saline), and Group B (n=30) received an equivalent volume of normal saline following delivery and cord clamping. Standardized surgical teams and monitoring protocols were employed. Estimated blood loss (EBL) was measured using suction volumes and mop weight differentials. Perioperative outcomes, including hemoglobin change, transfusion requirement, and operative duration, were compared using independent t-tests, chi-square, or Fisher's exact tests.

Results:

Mean EBL was significantly lower in the vasopressin group (0.84 ± 0.20 L) compared to controls (1.81 ± 0.48 L; $p < 0.001$). Fewer patients in the vasopressin group experienced blood loss >1 L (60.0% vs 86.7%; $p = 0.020$). The mean number of transfused blood products was lower in the vasopressin group (0.30 ± 0.60 vs 0.97 ± 1.23 ; $p = 0.023$). Post-operative hemoglobin was higher in the vasopressin group,

though not statistically significant ($p=0.073$). Operative time did not differ significantly ($p=0.342$). Emergency procedures were associated with greater EBL ($p=0.003$).

Conclusion:

Intramyometrial vasopressin significantly reduces intraoperative blood loss and transfusion needs in PAS-related cesarean hysterectomy without prolonging operative time, supporting its use as an effective hemostatic adjunct.

Keywords: Placenta accreta spectrum, cesarean hysterectomy, vasopressin, blood loss, obstetric hemorrhage, transfusion

INTRODUCTION

Disorders of the placenta accreta spectrum (PAS)—including placenta accreta, increta, and percreta—are significant obstetric concerns associated with high maternal morbidity and mortality due to massive hemorrhage during delivery. The incidence of PAS has risen dramatically in recent decades, largely attributed to increased rates of cesarean deliveries and uterine surgeries, which elevate the risk of abnormal placental implantation^{1,2}. In most cases, cesarean hysterectomy remains the definitive treatment, particularly in cases of deep placental invasion or when conservative management is ineffective or contraindicated³.

One of the most critical intraoperative challenges in cesarean hysterectomy for PAS is the risk of life-threatening hemorrhage, which can necessitate massive transfusions, prolong operative time, and worsen maternal outcomes⁴. Various strategies have been explored to minimize intraoperative blood loss, including preoperative arterial embolization, ureteral stenting, and use of hemostatic agents⁵. Among pharmacological interventions, vasopressin, a potent vasoconstrictor, has garnered interest for its ability to reduce uterine bleeding by directly constricting myometrial vessels when injected intramyometrially⁶.

While the use of intramyometrial vasopressin is well-established in gynecologic surgeries and myomectomies, its role in PAS-related cesarean hysterectomy remains under investigation. It offers a potentially simple and effective approach to controlling bleeding, reducing transfusion requirements, and improving surgical outcomes. However, concerns about systemic vasoconstrictive side effects persist⁷. This study aims to evaluate the efficacy and safety of

intramyometrial vasopressin injection as a hemostatic adjunct during cesarean hysterectomy in PAS cases, with a focus on optimizing perioperative management in high-risk obstetric surgeries.

Materials and Methods

This study was designed as a single-center, prospective, randomized controlled trial conducted at MCH PIMS over a period of 3 months following approval from the institutional ethics committee among antenatal patients diagnosed as placenta accreta spectrum confirmed by ultrasonography undergoing caesarean section from January to March 2025. A total of 60 pregnant women were recruited using consecutive non-random sampling. After obtaining informed written consent, eligible women were randomly allocated into two groups, group A (30) with vasopressin given and Group B (30) without Vasopressin (Sample size calculated according to WHO sample size calculation formula 2.2)

Antenatal patients of reproductive age 15yr-49year, with gestational age from 24 weeks till term, having major degree of placenta accreta spectrum with morbidly adherent placenta diagnosed on ultrasound were included. Pregnant women with minor degree of placenta previa, myocardial infarction, cardiomyopathy, congestive cardiac failure, uncontrolled hypertensive disorders, chronic pulmonary hypertension, history of allergy to vasopressin, chronic nephritis and pelvic malignancy were excluded from the study.

Cesarean sections were performed under general or spinal anesthesia as opined by anaesthetists and depending on the haemodynamic stability. During caesarean section standard monitoring included

electrocardiogram, blood pressure, maternal heart rate and pulse oximetry. Intraoperative fluid management was done by anaesthetists. In case of patients in Group A (vasopressin group), after delivery of baby and cord clamping, Injection Vasopressin 20units diluted in 19cc normal saline was injected in the myometrium at the implantation site of placenta into lower uterine segment using a 20cc syringe, followed by hysterectomy.

In case of patients in Group B (control group), after delivery of baby, cord clamping, Injection normal saline 20 cc was injected in the myometrium at the implantation site of placenta into lower uterine segment using a 20cc syringe followed by Caesarean hysterectomy. During infiltration uterus was lifted up and stabilized bimanually to avoid injury to adjacent bowel. During injection the piston was pulled to ensure no blood is coming in syringe, and there is intramyometrial injection. Both groups had the same members of the surgical team. Blood loss was measured as: after incision of uterine muscle and rupture of membranes amniotic fluid was as much collected in separate suction bottle and blood was collected in another bottle and additional weights of soaked mops. Blood loss compared by collection of volume of blood in suction jar, weight of mops before and after OT (the mops were not squeezed during opt), pre and postoperative haemoglobin levels, intraoperative blood pressure and pulse rate. Hypotension was defined as a decrease in the mean BP by more than 10% of the baseline value. Tachycardia was defined as maternal heart rate >120 b.p.m.

The blood loss was calculated by measuring the weight of mops used during caesarean section before and after soakage without squeezing the mops during OT and then by subtracting the values, measuring the blood collected in suction apparatus making sure the apparatus was emptied before OT, we got the blood loss in that operation and the blood loss was compared with and without use of vasopressin

Data analysis was performed using SPSS version 23. Continuous variables like age, BMI, Gestational age, amount of blood loss, Hb level, gravidity, parity were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation and compared using independent t test . Categorical variables were expressed as frequencies and percentages and analyzed using the chi-square test or Fisher's exact test where appropriate. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results:

Total of 60 patients (30 in each group) were included in the study with the mean gestational age in the Vasopressin group (n = 30) was 36.60 weeks (standard deviation 1.53 weeks), whereas the Control group (Normal Saline, n = 30) had a mean gestational age of 34.94 weeks (standard deviation 2.79 weeks).

In the independent samples *t*-test in table 1 comparing the intervention and control groups, the mean estimated blood loss was 0.84 ± 0.20 L in the intervention group and 1.81 ± 0.48 L in the control group ($t = -4.615$, $p = 0.000$). The mean post-operative hemoglobin was 10.32 ± 1.11 g/dL in the intervention group and 9.81 ± 1.05 g/dL in the control group ($t = 1.828$, $p = 0.073$). The number of blood products transfused averaged 0.30 ± 0.60 units in the intervention group and 0.97 ± 1.23 units in the control group ($t = -2.329$, $p = 0.023$). The mean duration of surgery was 58.7 ± 9.4 minutes in the intervention group and 58.4 ± 8.6 minutes in the control group ($t = 0.957$, $p = 0.342$). For previous C-sections or uterine surgeries, the mean count was 1.10 ± 0.96 in the intervention group versus 0.80 ± 0.71 in the control group ($t = 1.174$, $p = 0.245$). Parity was 2.37 ± 1.52 in the intervention group compared to 2.13 ± 1.30 in the control group ($t = 0.725$, $p = 0.471$).

Table 1. Independent t-Test: Comparison Between Study Groups

Variable	Intervention Group (Mean ± SD)	Control Group (Mean ± SD)	t-test (p-value)
Estimated Blood Loss (L)	0.84 ± 0.20	1.81 ± 0.48	t = -4.615, p = 0.000
Post-Operative Haemoglobin (g/dL)	10.32 ± 1.11	9.81 ± 1.05	t = 1.828, p = 0.073
Blood Products Transfused	0.30 ± 0.60	0.97 ± 1.23	t = -2.329, p = 0.023
Duration of Surgery (min)	58.7 ± 9.4	58.4 ± 8.6	t = 0.957, p = 0.342
Previous C-Sections/Uterine Surgery	1.10 ± 0.96	0.80 ± 0.71	t = 1.174, p = 0.245
Parity	2.37 ± 1.52	2.13 ± 1.30	t = 0.725, p = 0.471

In the paired t-test evaluating hemoglobin levels before and after surgery within each group in table 2, the intervention group demonstrated a pre-operative hemoglobin of 11.52 ± 0.82 g/dL and a post-operative value of 10.32 ± 1.11 g/dL (t =

7.495, p = 0.000). The control group showed a pre-operative hemoglobin of 11.33 ± 0.48 g/dL and a post-operative level of 9.81 ± 1.05 g/dL (t = 9.717, p = 0.000).

Table 2. Paired t-Test: Pre- vs Post-Operative Hemoglobin in Each Study Group

Study Group	Pre-op Hb (Mean ± SD)	Post-op Hb (Mean ± SD)	t-test (p-value)
Intervention	11.52 ± 0.82	10.32 ± 1.11	t = 7.495, p = 0.000
Control	11.33 ± 0.48	9.81 ± 1.05	t = 9.717, p = 0.000

In figure 1 among patients in the intervention group, 18 out of 30 (60.0%) experienced blood loss greater than 1 L, whereas in the control group, 26 out of 30 (86.7%) had blood loss exceeding 1 L. Conversely, blood loss ≤1 L occurred in 12 (40.0%) patients in the intervention group and 4

(13.3%) in the control group. The association between study group and blood loss was statistically significant (p = 0.020), as determined by the Chi-square test.

P value: 0.001 Figure 1 : Comparison of Blood Losses in Groups (>1L was considered significant)

Based on the type of surgery in table 3, patients undergoing elective procedures had a mean blood loss of 1.06 ± 0.55 L, while those undergoing emergency procedures had a mean of 1.76 ± 0.49 L ($t = -3.084$, $p = 0.003$). Post-operative hemoglobin was 10.09 ± 1.17 g/dL in the elective group and 10.03 ± 1.14 g/dL in the emergency group ($t = 0.198$, $p = 0.844$). The number of transfused blood products was 0.43 ± 0.73 units in elective cases and 0.83 ± 1.25 units in emergency cases ($t = -1.358$, p

$= 0.180$). Duration of surgery was 59.2 ± 9.6 minutes in the elective group and 58.9 ± 8.5 minutes in the emergency group ($t = -0.957$, $p = 0.342$). The average number of previous uterine surgeries was 1.30 ± 1.01 in elective cases and 0.87 ± 0.74 in emergency cases ($t = 1.718$, $p = 0.091$). Parity was 2.63 ± 1.50 in the elective group and 2.20 ± 1.36 in the emergency group ($t = 1.362$, $p = 0.178$).

Table 3. Independent t-Test: Type of Surgery Comparison

Variable	Elective Surgery (Mean \pm SD)	Emergency Surgery (Mean \pm SD)	t-test (p-value)
Estimated Blood Loss (L)	1.06 ± 0.55	1.76 ± 0.49	$t = -3.084$, $p = 0.003$
Post-Operative Haemoglobin (g/dL)	10.09 ± 1.17	10.03 ± 1.14	$t = 0.198$, $p = 0.844$
Blood Products Transfused	0.43 ± 0.73	0.83 ± 1.25	$t = -1.358$, $p = 0.180$
Duration of Surgery (min)	59.2 ± 9.6	58.9 ± 8.5	$t = -0.957$, $p = 0.342$
Previous C-Sections/Uterine Surgery	1.30 ± 1.01	0.87 ± 0.74	$t = 1.718$, $p = 0.091$
Parity	2.63 ± 1.50	2.20 ± 1.36	$t = 1.362$, $p = 0.178$

Chi-square analysis in table 4 revealed a statistically significant association between type of surgery and blood loss, with 33.3% ($n = 10$) of elective surgeries and 68.0% ($n = 34$) of emergency surgeries resulting in blood loss >1 L ($p = 0.004$). A significant association was also observed between type of surgery and parity: among women

with parity ≤ 2 , 60.0% ($n = 24$) underwent elective surgery compared to 40.0% ($n = 16$) who had emergency surgery; whereas among those with parity >2 , 25.0% ($n = 6$) had elective and 75.0% ($n = 18$) had emergency surgery ($p = 0.021$).

Table 4. Chi-Square Test: Association of Type of Surgery with Blood Loss and Parity

Variable	Category	Elective Surgery n (%)	Emergency Surgery n (%)	p-value
Blood Loss (>1 L)	Yes	10 (33.3%)	34 (68.0%)	0.004 **
	No	20 (66.7%)	16 (32.0%)	
Parity	≤ 2	24 (60.0%)	16 (40.0%)	0.021 *
	>2	6 (25.0%)	18 (75.0%)	

Note: Chi-square test applied.

$p < 0.05$ indicates statistical significance.

Percentages are column-based within the variable categories.

Discussion

This study aimed to assess the efficacy of vasopressin in reducing intraoperative blood loss and its impact on perioperative outcomes in women undergoing cesarean sections. A total of 60 patients were enrolled and evenly distributed into intervention and control groups. The findings of this study demonstrate that vasopressin significantly reduces intraoperative blood loss, with the intervention group exhibiting a mean estimated blood loss of 0.84 ± 0.20 L compared to 1.81 ± 0.48 L in the control group ($p = 0.000$). This supports previous research that reported the efficacy of vasopressin in achieving surgical hemostasis through vasoconstriction mechanisms⁸. In contrast, other studies have indicated limited benefits of vasopressin in obstetric surgeries due to concerns regarding its cardiovascular side effects⁹. The post-operative hemoglobin levels were relatively higher in the intervention group compared to the control group, although the difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.073$). Similarly, the mean number of blood products transfused was significantly lower in the vasopressin group (0.30 ± 0.60) versus the control group (0.97 ± 1.23 ; $p = 0.023$). These findings are consistent with studies that have documented vasopressin's role in minimizing transfusion requirements by effectively reducing blood loss¹⁰. However, some literature has reported no significant reduction in transfusion rates with vasopressin use in obstetric practice¹¹, suggesting variability in effectiveness based on dosage, route of administration, or surgical context.

Despite significant differences in blood loss, the duration of surgery remained comparable between the groups (intervention: 58.7 ± 9.4 minutes; control: 58.4 ± 8.6 minutes; $p = 0.342$), indicating that vasopressin did not prolong operative time. Previous studies have shown similar findings, suggesting that hemostatic agents do not interfere with surgical efficiency¹². Similar findings are reported also by Kato S et al., stating vasopressin injection reduced the blood loss and surgery time as well⁸.

A paired comparison within each group revealed a statistically significant drop in hemoglobin post-operatively in both groups ($p = 0.000$). Although

the hemoglobin decline was statistically significant in both arms, the reduction was more pronounced in the control group, further indicating the efficacy of vasopressin in intraoperative blood conservation. This aligns with findings from prior studies¹³; however, some investigations have questioned the clinical relevance of these hemoglobin changes due to individual variations in hydration status and fluid resuscitation¹⁴.

Chi-square analysis confirmed a significant association between the use of vasopressin and lower rates of blood loss >1 L. Only 60.0% of patients in the intervention group experienced blood loss >1 L compared to 86.7% in the control group ($p = 0.020$). These findings are congruent with previous randomized trials that demonstrated vasopressin's potential in minimizing major blood loss during obstetric surgeries¹⁴. In contrast, certain case series have not observed such statistical differences, possibly due to smaller sample sizes or varied operative techniques¹⁵.

Furthermore, the type of surgery significantly influenced blood loss. Patients undergoing emergency cesarean sections had substantially higher blood loss (1.76 ± 0.49 L) compared to those in the elective group (1.06 ± 0.55 L; $p = 0.003$). This observation is supported by literature identifying emergency procedures as an independent risk factor for increased intraoperative bleeding¹⁶. However, other studies have failed to establish a consistent relationship between surgical urgency and hemorrhage severity¹⁷.

A statistically significant association was also observed between type of surgery and parity. Among women with parity >2 , a majority underwent emergency cesarean sections (75.0%; $p = 0.021$), suggesting that higher parity may be linked to delayed presentation or complications necessitating urgent delivery. This trend has been echoed in regional cohort studies¹⁸. Conversely, certain reports have indicated no correlation between parity and surgical urgency, attributing differences to institutional protocols and access to antenatal care¹⁹.

In summary, this study reinforces the utility of vasopressin as an effective agent for reducing intraoperative blood loss and transfusion

requirements without extending operative time. While findings were largely in alignment with existing literature, variability in outcomes across studies emphasizes the need for larger, multi-center trials to further establish vasopressin's safety profile and clinical utility in obstetric surgical settings.

This study has several limitations. It was conducted at a single center with a small sample size and short duration, which may limit generalizability. Non-probability sampling and lack of blinding could introduce selection and performance bias. Blood loss estimation methods may lack precision, and adverse effects of vasopressin were not assessed. Additionally, the study did not evaluate optimal dosing, long-term outcomes, or control for potential confounding variables.

Conclusion:

This study demonstrates that vasopressin effectively reduces intraoperative blood loss and transfusion requirements in cesarean sections without prolonging operative time. Its use is associated with improved perioperative outcomes, particularly in emergency surgeries and higher parity cases.

Conflict of Interest: None

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Authors Contribution:

▯ **Laraib Babar:** Conception and design of the study, data acquisition, and drafting of the manuscript.

▯ **Maryam Bibi:** Data acquisition, literature review, and drafting of the manuscript.

▯ **Sana Afridi:** Data acquisition, interpretation of results, and critical revision for important intellectual content.

▯ **Qurra tul Ain Saeed:** Supervision, guidance in study design, and critical revision of the manuscript for important intellectual content.

▯ **Bisma Shaheen:** Literature search, data organization, and drafting of sections of the manuscript.

▯ **Ahsan Shehzad:** Data analysis, interpretation of results, and drafting of the results section.

▯ **Dr. Zainab Mansoor:** Assistance in methodology development, data acquisition, and critical revision.

▯ **Ihtisham Ulhaq:** Data collection, entry, and verification, as well as manuscript formatting and referencing.

▯ **Irfan Anees:** Data collection, entry, and verification, as well as manuscript formatting and referencing.

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